

FUNCTIONAL ASPECTS OF PUNCTUATION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: The article explores the significance of punctuation in achieving communicative competence. This article delves into the functional aspects of punctuation within the realm of linguistics, shedding light on its dual roles of division and specification. The study examines how punctuation marks contribute to the syntactic organization of text, dividing it into coherent units, while also serving the crucial function of specifying and emphasizing elements within a linguistic context.

Keywords: functional aspects of punctuation, expressiveness of speech, stylistic features, comparative analysis.

INTRODUCTION.

Punctuation, often regarded as a set of rules guiding the use of symbols, holds a pivotal role in linguistics. Beyond its surface-level application, punctuation serves deeper functional purposes, influencing syntactic structure and emphasizing specific linguistic elements. The findings underscore the intricate relationship between punctuation and linguistic structure. Punctuation marks act as guides, helping readers navigate the syntactic landscape while also allowing writers to convey emphasis and specificity. The discussion delves into the implications of these functional aspects on effective communication.

The total number of punctuation marks used in our current writing is ten, each of them has its own graphic form; they are used for specific purposes in written speech and perform a specific task. Each punctuation mark has its own function and purpose. Punctuation marks can be grouped according to their use as follows:

1. Punctuation marks used at the end of the sentence: full stop, question marks and exclamation marks;
2. Punctuation marks used in the sentence: comma;
3. Mixed punctuation marks: 1) those used at the beginning and in the middle of a sentence: hyphen; 2) those used at the end and in the middle of the sentence: colon and semicolon; 3) those used at the beginning, middle and end of the sentence: quotation marks, parentheses and full stops.

It is known that punctuation marks used at the end of sentences in English and Uzbek are made up of period, question and exclamation marks, and their places of use differ from each other in different system languages. In order to clarify our opinion, we will analyze the cases of use of the dot in English.

1) In English, the dot differs depending on the options, i.e. full stop - British option; period - used in the American version, it expresses a complete thought as in other languages, and comes at the end of the sentence regardless of the type of sentence.

- *"I run three miles every morning."* (declarative sentence)
- *"I could study better if you turned down the music."* (conditional sentence)
- *"Please start the car."* (imperative sentence).

In Uzbek, unlike English, a dot is used at the end of a sentence to indicate that the thought is complete. It is known that the meaning of the message is expressed from the figurative sentences, the event is emphasized. They can also be used to understand meanings such as request, advice, desire, suspicion, determination. "Darak sentences have a calm tone, falling intonation, and the intonation is very low, especially in the last part (the last syllable of the last word)." This is the point intonation.

Sentences with a period at the end are structurally simple, complex, compound, one-part and two-part, complete and incomplete. For example:

- *Hozir men Toshkentdaman.*
- *Qor. Sovuq. Bo'ronning o'chmagan uni.*
- Ayozning zabtidan saltirar daraxt.*

It is worth noting that in English, demonstrative sentences can be turned into exclamations to express strong emotions, depending on the writer's purpose. For example, we change the above English sentences into exclamatory sentences:

- *"I run three miles every morning!"*
- *"I could study better if you turned down the music!"*
- *"Please start the car!"*

In English, a period is also used at the end of demonstrative sentences containing an interrogative sentence, for example:

- *"Jane asked Paul if he was hungry."*
- *"I wonder what has happened."*
- *"She asked him if the bus had left."*

The English language also has its own characteristics in the use of the full stop, and this situation can often be found in quotations. However, in the American version, the period is in quotation marks, which means:

-The CEO said, "This is a great day for the company."

The next sign used at the end of a sentence is a question mark, which in both languages means a complete thought and a question, used at the end of a sentence to clarify something. For example:

"How are you feeling?"

"This weather is wonderful, isn't it?"

Unlike English, interrogative sentences in Uzbek have two forms, namely:

a) interrogative grammatical means are involved:

- Endi ketib qolmaysizmi?

Ha, nima, uyalasanmi, kap-katta qiz-a? (G'.G'.);

b) grammatical means indicating a question are not involved, in which the meaning of the question is determined by a question mark in writing, and by intonation in oral speech:

- To'ygacha qo'limni ham ushlatmayman deysiz chog'i? (Uyg'un).

Also, in English and Uzbek languages, a question mark is used to express a question in a quotation:

The lady asked, 'Where are you going?'

The boss inquired, 'Is Mr. Brown still away on business?'

It is known that in every language the meaning of the sentence is expressed by means of punctuation marks, and they are divided into groups according to their function. So, in English and Uzbek languages, commas, semicolons, colons and dashes are the punctuation marks used in sentences, and commas are used in them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

R. Kongurov, E. Begmatov and Y. Tajiyev, who studied the issue of speech culture on the example of the Uzbek language, define literary standards as follows: it is understood to apply the preferred option". Another Uzbek linguist A. Mamatov explains 23 features of the norm in his work on literary standards.

Based on the above-mentioned opinions of English, Russian and Uzbek linguists, the literary standard can be defined as follows: the literary standard reflects the history and present, social life of a particular nation, has dynamic and variable characteristics. are language units or language forms whose use by language speakers is accepted as a normative situation.

As a result of research conducted in the field of speech culture, there is still no consensus on the meaning of such terms as norm, language norms, literary language norm in linguistics. It should be noted that the concepts of standard and literary language do not have a clear definition in special literature. Often, "the norm is described as a 'set of laws' rather than a system of rules." In some definitions, we can see that the authors treat the concepts of standard (language) and literary standard as synonyms, "pronunciation rules, grammar and other language tools, rules of vocabulary adopted in the practice of educated speech" .A number of foreign linguists emphasized the need to refer to imperfect speech in the process of clarifying speech-creating tools. In this sense, in foreign psycholinguistics, special attention is paid to the study of speech errors, that is, the expression of hesitation (hesitation), specific methods of correcting speech errors.

The issue of researching punctuation norms occupies an important place in the field of linguistics. Analyzing and studying this aspect is divided into different directions:

- theoretical aspects O.V. Dolgova (Aleksandrova), L.U. Arapiyeva, L.L. Baranova, N.S. Valgina, L.M. Kolsova, T.M. Nikolayeva, N.N. Orekhova, A.M. Peshkovsky, B.S. Schwarzkopf, N.L. Shubina, L.V. It was studied by linguists like Sherba;
- from a stylistic point of view G.N. Akimova, A.V. Desyatova, V.V. Jilsova, Y.M. Lotman, B.S. Schwarzkopf, A.D. Scientists such as Shmelyov have researched;
- changes in the historical series of the punctuation front were considered by N.S.Valgina, N.N.Orekhova, B.I.Osipov, B.S.Schwarskopf;
- S.I. Abakumova, V.V. Babayseva developed methodical principles of punctuation.

The expression of the theoretical rules of punctuation is mainly reflected in the framework of sentence fragments and types. Later, studies whose object became a set of punctuation rules focused on studying the aspects of expression in the text. When referring to the text related to these issues, "punctuation marks are expressed in texts connected to each other according to their function, including various mixed and completely different syntactic constructions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In English, it depends on the purpose of the writer to turn demonstrative sentences into exclamatory sentences to express strong emotions, and imperative sentences with a period at the end have their own lexical-grammatical and intonation signs. Similar aspects of the signs at the end of the

sentence in English and Uzbek are that 1) in the names of some abbreviations, in addition to acronyms, which are a type of abbreviations, when a person's name is abbreviated, a period is indicated before the closing parenthesis. It should be noted that there are differences between the English variants in the use of the noun with words denoting occupation or address.

The punctuation marks used in the sentence have similar and unique aspects in the places of use, and when separating the combined clauses, the sentences in the compound sentence without a connector are used at the same time or consecutively. When indicating events, introductory and exclamatory words and referring nouns come at the beginning, in the middle or at the end of the sentence, they are separated by a comma. However, in English, the sequence of lexemes of the adjective word group, formed on the basis of the order of adjectives, is expressed without a comma.

CONCLUSION

If punctuation marks in a text are collectively explained regarding their functions, it can lead to difficulties in comprehending the sentence's content. The conventions and regulations for employing punctuation marks, influenced by speech forms and functional styles in literary language, adhere to stylistic principles. Texts are categorized based on meaning and content. Consequently, every punctuation mark in a text, beyond its standardized usage, possesses aspects that influence the text's meaning and can potentially bring about significant alterations if needed. This reliance rests solely on the reader's understanding and perspective.

In the analysis of the use of punctuation marks in the actual process of written communication, taking into account the communicative interaction between the human factor, that is, the writer and the reader, makes it possible to determine the expression of punctuation marks. It is worth noting that pragmalinguistic features are expressed in sentences with exclamation marks, and it was found that the positive meaning in the text means surprise, and the negative one shows an ironic tone.

Segmenting the text through the use of punctuation marks plays a crucial role in ensuring the writer's creative ideas are effectively conveyed to the reader. This implies a shared understanding between the writer and reader regarding the interpretation of these signs. In essence, the creation and reception of the text should adhere to a unified set of rules. Punctuation, in this context, becomes a societal phenomenon, serving to articulate the

demands of written communication, and is mutually understood by both the writer and the reader

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